

TQM PRACTICES AND PERFORMANCE OF PROJECTS IMPLEMENTED UNDER THE BLUE ECONOMY INITIATIVE IN KENYA'S COAST REGION.

***Martin Otundo Richard**

PhD Fellow in Project Management, JKUAT_Kenya

A Freelance Researcher, A Data Analyst, A Project Manager, Senior Consultant in Project Management and Blue Economy

Contacts: martinotundo@gmail.com; +254721246744/+254759819660

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of Total Quality Management (TQM) practices on the performance of Blue Economy projects in Kenya's coastal region. The research employed a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews to analyze the effectiveness of TQM principles such as leadership commitment, process management, customer focus, and continuous improvement. The study targeted project managers, team members, and stakeholders involved in Blue Economy projects, with a total sample of 116 respondents. Descriptive and inferential statistical analyses, including ANOVA and regression tests, were utilized to evaluate the data.

The findings indicate that TQM practices significantly enhance project performance, with leadership commitment and continuous improvement showing the strongest positive effects. Process management and customer focus also positively impact project outcomes, although challenges such as resistance to change and integration difficulties were noted. The study's results align with existing literature, confirming the critical role of TQM in improving efficiency, quality, and stakeholder satisfaction in the Blue Economy sector.

The research concludes that effective TQM implementation is essential for the success of Blue Economy projects. Recommendations include enhancing leadership training, addressing process management challenges, strengthening customer focus, and promoting continuous improvement. Future research should explore the impact of TQM on specific Blue Economy sectors, conduct longitudinal studies, and investigate contextual challenges to provide a deeper understanding of TQM practices in varying environments.

Key terms: Total Quality Management (TQM), Blue Economy projects, Kenya's coastal region, leadership commitment, process management, customer focus, continuous improvement, project performance, statistical analysis, stakeholder satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

The Blue Economy initiative, emphasizing the sustainable use of ocean resources for economic growth, improved livelihoods, and job creation, has gained significant attention globally. In Kenya, particularly along the coast region, this initiative has become a critical focus due to the region's rich maritime resources. The successful implementation of projects under the Blue Economy framework requires a robust management approach, with Total Quality Management (TQM) being a key driver for enhancing project performance and ensuring sustainability.

TQM, as a comprehensive management philosophy, emphasizes continuous improvement, customer satisfaction, and involvement of all employees. Its application in project management aims to improve efficiency, reduce waste, and increase stakeholder satisfaction.

In the context of Kenya's coast region, where the Blue Economy is seen as a potential catalyst for economic transformation, understanding the impact of TQM practices on project performance is crucial. This study explores the extent to which TQM practices are integrated into the management of Blue Economy projects and assesses their effect on project outcomes. It examines various TQM dimensions, including leadership commitment, process management, employee involvement, and continuous improvement, and how these factors contribute to the success or failure of projects.

The relevance of this research is underscored by the Kenyan government's strategic emphasis on the Blue Economy as a means to diversify the economy and create jobs. With the global shift towards sustainable economic practices, this study provides valuable insights into how TQM can enhance the efficacy and sustainability of Blue Economy projects. The findings aim to inform policymakers, project managers, and stakeholders on best practices for implementing TQM in this critical sector, thereby contributing to the broader discourse on sustainable development in coastal regions.

This research employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive analysis of TQM practices and project performance. The study focuses on projects implemented in the coast region of Kenya, utilizing case studies, surveys, and interviews with key stakeholders. By assessing the impact of TQM on project outcomes, this study seeks to identify key success factors and potential challenges, offering recommendations for future projects within the Blue Economy framework.

For better introduction, a definition of terms in the topic is important and accordingly, here is a definition of key terms:

Total Quality Management (TQM):

TQM refers to a systematic management approach centered around continuous improvement, customer focus, and the active participation of all members of an organization in improving processes, products, and services. It aims to enhance efficiency, reduce defects, and ensure customer satisfaction by integrating quality management principles across all organizational activities (Evans and Lindsay 2017).

It is in order to know that the Proponents of Total Quality Management (TQM) can be well understood from its evolution. Therefore, Total Quality Management (TQM) has evolved significantly over the years, influenced by contributions from various scholars and practitioners. Key proponents of TQM and their contributions include: **W. Edwards Deming (1900-1993)**: Deming is widely regarded as one of the pioneers of TQM. His work emphasized the importance of statistical quality control and continuous improvement. Deming's "14 Points for Management" and the "Plan-Do-Check-Act" (PDCA) cycle laid the foundation for TQM principles (Deming 1986). **Joseph M. Juran (1904-2008)**: Juran contributed to TQM by focusing on quality planning, quality control, and quality improvement. His concept of the "Juran Trilogy" highlights these three critical aspects of quality management. Juran also emphasized the role of top management in leading quality initiatives (Juran 1989). **Philip B. Crosby (1926-2001)**: Crosby introduced the concept of "zero defects" and advocated for the idea that quality should be defined as conformance to requirements. He emphasized the cost of poor quality and the importance of prevention over inspection (Crosby 1979). **Kaoru Ishikawa (1915-1989)**: Ishikawa is known for developing the "Ishikawa" or "fishbone" diagram, a tool

for identifying the root causes of quality problems. He also promoted the concept of "company-wide quality control," emphasizing the involvement of all employees in the quality process (Ishikawa 1985).

TQM has evolved from quality control practices that focused primarily on inspection and detection of defects to a comprehensive management philosophy that integrates quality into every aspect of an organization's operations. The evolution can be traced through several key phases: **Quality Inspection (Pre-1940s)**: Emphasis on inspecting finished products to detect and correct defects. **Statistical Quality Control (1940s-1950s)**: Introduction of statistical methods for quality control, spearheaded by Deming and others. **Quality Assurance (1960s-1970s)**: Focus on preventing defects through systematic quality planning and control. **Total Quality Management (1980s-present)**: A holistic approach that integrates quality into all organizational processes, with a focus on continuous improvement, customer satisfaction, and employee involvement.

TQM consists of several core elements, each with specific indicators of success: **Leadership Commitment**: Top management's active involvement and commitment to quality initiatives. Indicators include the establishment of quality policies, setting quality goals, and allocating resources for quality improvement. **Customer Focus**: Understanding and meeting customer needs and expectations. Indicators include customer satisfaction surveys, customer feedback mechanisms, and measures of customer loyalty. **Employee Involvement**: Engaging all employees in quality improvement efforts. Indicators include training programs, employee suggestion schemes, and recognition of quality achievements. **Process Management**: Systematic management of processes to ensure consistent quality. Indicators include process documentation, process performance metrics, and continuous process improvement initiatives. **Continuous Improvement**: Ongoing efforts to improve products, services, and processes. Indicators include the implementation of PDCA cycles, benchmarking, and the adoption of best practices. **Fact-based Decision Making**: Using data and analysis to guide decisions. Indicators include the use of statistical tools, data-driven problem-solving, and performance measurement.

TQM's principles are highly applicable to the implementation of Blue Economy projects, particularly in the context of sustainable development. In these projects, quality management is essential to ensure the effective use of marine resources, adherence to environmental regulations, and the delivery of benefits to local communities. **Leadership Commitment**: Strong leadership is necessary to align Blue Economy projects with sustainability goals and secure stakeholder support. **Customer Focus**: Understanding the needs of diverse stakeholders, including local communities, tourists, and investors, is crucial for project success. **Employee Involvement**: Engaging local communities and employees in quality initiatives can enhance project ownership and sustainability. **Process Management**: Efficient management of project processes, such as resource extraction and waste management, ensures minimal environmental impact. **Continuous Improvement**: The dynamic nature of marine ecosystems requires continuous adaptation and improvement of project practices. **Fact-based Decision Making**: Data collection and analysis are vital for monitoring the environmental and social impact of Blue Economy projects.

By integrating TQM principles, Blue Economy projects can achieve sustainable development, optimize resource use, and enhance stakeholder satisfaction.

Performance:

In the context of project management, performance refers to the degree to which a project achieves its goals and objectives. It encompasses various dimensions, including time, cost,

quality, and stakeholder satisfaction. Performance is measured by evaluating project outcomes against predefined criteria and standards (Kerzner 2019).

Projects:

Projects are temporary endeavors undertaken to create a unique product, service, or result. They are characterized by a defined scope, timeline, budget, and specific objectives. In this research, projects refer to those initiated under the Blue Economy initiative in Kenya's coast region (PMI 2021).

Blue Economy:

The Blue Economy is an economic framework that promotes sustainable use of ocean resources for economic growth, improved livelihoods, and job creation while preserving the health of ocean ecosystems. It encompasses various sectors, including fisheries, tourism, renewable energy, and maritime transport (World Bank 2017).

Initiative:

An initiative is a strategic plan or program undertaken to address specific goals or challenges. In this context, the Blue Economy initiative refers to the collective efforts and projects aimed at leveraging Kenya's coastal and marine resources for sustainable development (Kenya Vision 2030).

Kenya's Coast Region:

This refers to the geographical area along Kenya's coastline bordering the Indian Ocean. It includes counties such as Mombasa, Kilifi, Kwale, Lamu, Tana River, and Taita-Taveta. The region is rich in marine and coastal resources and is a focal point for Blue Economy activities (Kenya National Bureau of Statistics 2020).

BACKGROUND TO THE STUDY

Global Perspective

The concept of the Blue Economy has gained prominence globally as a strategic approach to sustainably harness the vast potential of oceans, seas, and coastal areas. According to the World Bank (2017), the Blue Economy encompasses the sustainable use of ocean resources for economic growth, improved livelihoods, and jobs, while preserving the health of ocean ecosystems. The global ocean economy is projected to double in size by 2030, driven by sectors such as marine biotechnology, aquaculture, coastal and marine tourism, and offshore renewable energy (OECD 2016). This anticipated growth presents both opportunities and challenges, necessitating effective management practices like Total Quality Management (TQM) to ensure sustainable development.

A practical case is the European Union's Blue Growth strategy, which aims to harness the potential of Europe's oceans, seas, and coasts for job creation and economic growth. The strategy prioritizes sustainable development in sectors like marine renewable energy, aquaculture, and coastal tourism. The EU has established comprehensive frameworks and regulations to manage and protect its marine resources, emphasizing sustainable practices (European Commission 2012).

Continental Perspective

On the African continent, the African Union's Agenda 2063 underscores the importance of the Blue Economy as a catalyst for economic transformation. The African Union (AU) recognizes

the continent's vast maritime resources as critical to achieving sustainable development and poverty reduction. The African Charter on Maritime Security, Safety, and Development in Africa (Lomé Charter) emphasizes the need for cooperation among African states to develop and manage marine resources sustainably (AU 2014).

South Africa is a notable example of a country advancing its Blue Economy. Through Operation Phakisa, the government has developed an integrated approach to unlocking the economic potential of its oceans. The initiative focuses on expanding sectors such as marine transport, offshore oil and gas exploration, aquaculture, and coastal tourism. South Africa's commitment to sustainable practices is reflected in its emphasis on marine spatial planning, environmental protection, and community engagement (South African Government 2014).

Regional Perspective

In the East African region, the Blue Economy is gaining traction as a key economic driver, especially for countries with significant coastal and marine resources. The Indian Ocean Rim Association (IORA) has been instrumental in promoting regional cooperation in the sustainable management of the Indian Ocean's resources. IORA's Blue Economy initiatives focus on enhancing maritime safety and security, promoting sustainable fisheries, and supporting marine and coastal tourism (IORA 2015).

Seychelles is a regional leader in the Blue Economy, having established a Ministry dedicated to the sector. The country's Blue Economy roadmap emphasizes sustainable use and conservation of marine resources, development of sustainable fisheries, and promotion of eco-friendly marine tourism. Seychelles has also pioneered the use of blue bonds to finance sustainable ocean-based projects, showcasing innovative financing mechanisms to support Blue Economy initiatives (Seychelles Ministry of Finance, Trade and the Blue Economy 2018).

Local Background (Kenya)

Kenya, with its extensive coastline along the Indian Ocean, is poised to leverage its Blue Economy for national development. The Kenyan government has identified the Blue Economy as a priority area under its Vision 2030 development blueprint, aiming to harness marine resources for economic growth, food security, and job creation. The country's Blue Economy agenda focuses on key sectors such as fisheries, maritime transport, coastal and marine tourism, and marine spatial planning (Kenya Vision 2030 2018).

Kenya's practical case of advancing the Blue Economy is evident in the development of the Lamu Port-South Sudan-Ethiopia Transport (LAPSSET) Corridor project. LAPSSET is an ambitious infrastructure project that includes the construction of a new deep-water port at Lamu, a major component aimed at enhancing regional trade and maritime transport. The project also considers environmental sustainability, with measures to mitigate potential ecological impacts on the coastal and marine environment (LAPSSET Corridor Development Authority 2020).

Furthermore, Kenya hosted the first global Sustainable Blue Economy Conference in 2018, highlighting its commitment to promoting sustainable ocean resource management. The conference brought together over 18,000 participants from around the world, including heads of state, policymakers, and stakeholders, to discuss and share best practices for sustainable Blue Economy development (Republic of Kenya 2018).

In implementing Blue Economy projects, Kenya faces challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, limited financial resources, and the need for effective governance frameworks. There is also a growing recognition of the importance of integrating TQM practices in project

management to enhance efficiency, ensure quality, and promote sustainability. TQM's emphasis on continuous improvement, customer focus, and stakeholder engagement aligns with the goals of the Blue Economy, making it a valuable approach for managing projects in this sector.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Blue Economy represents a vital opportunity for coastal nations, including Kenya, to achieve sustainable economic growth. However, the implementation of Blue Economy projects is fraught with challenges, particularly in ensuring that these projects meet high standards of quality, sustainability, and stakeholder satisfaction. In Kenya's coast region, projects under the Blue Economy initiative have faced issues related to inefficient resource utilization, environmental degradation, and socio-economic disparities. The absence of robust management frameworks, such as Total Quality Management (TQM), exacerbates these problems by limiting the capacity to deliver high-quality outcomes that align with environmental and community needs.

Despite the global recognition of TQM as an effective management approach, its application in the context of Blue Economy projects in Kenya remains underexplored. There is a lack of comprehensive studies assessing how TQM practices can enhance the performance of these projects, particularly in terms of efficiency, sustainability, and stakeholder engagement. This gap in knowledge impedes the development of strategies that could improve project outcomes and ensure long-term benefits for the region. Thus, this study seeks to address the critical question: How can TQM practices be effectively integrated into the management of Blue Economy projects in Kenya's coast region to enhance project performance and sustainability?

Value of the Study

This study is valuable for several reasons. Firstly, it contributes to the academic discourse on the integration of TQM in the management of Blue Economy projects, an area with limited empirical research. By providing a detailed analysis of TQM practices and their impact on project performance, the study offers valuable insights for scholars and researchers interested in quality management and sustainable development.

Secondly, the findings of this study have practical implications for policymakers, project managers, and stakeholders involved in the Blue Economy. By identifying best practices and potential challenges in implementing TQM, the study provides a framework for improving project planning, execution, and evaluation. This can lead to more efficient resource use, reduced environmental impact, and greater socio-economic benefits for local communities.

Thirdly, the study's focus on Kenya's coast region aligns with the national development agenda, as articulated in Vision 2030, which prioritizes the Blue Economy as a key sector for economic growth. By addressing the specific challenges and opportunities in this region, the study supports national efforts to develop sustainable and inclusive economic policies. It also provides a model that can be replicated in other coastal regions in Kenya and beyond, thereby contributing to regional and global efforts toward sustainable ocean management.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The theoretical framework for this study is grounded in Total Quality Management (TQM) principles and their application to project management within the Blue Economy sector. TQM is a comprehensive management approach that emphasizes continuous improvement, customer satisfaction, and the active involvement of all organizational members in quality enhancement (Deming 1986; Juran 1989). This study will specifically utilize TQM's key elements—

leadership commitment, customer focus, employee involvement, process management, continuous improvement, and fact-based decision-making—as the primary theoretical constructs.

Leadership Commitment: This element emphasizes the role of top management in setting quality goals, providing resources, and creating a culture that values quality. In the context of Blue Economy projects, leadership commitment is crucial for aligning project objectives with sustainability goals and ensuring that all stakeholders are engaged in the quality management process.

Customer Focus: TQM highlights the importance of understanding and meeting customer needs. For Blue Economy projects, this includes a broad range of stakeholders, such as local communities, investors, government agencies, and environmental groups. A customer-focused approach ensures that projects are designed and implemented in a way that addresses the diverse needs and expectations of these stakeholders.

Employee Involvement: TQM advocates for the active participation of all employees in quality improvement efforts. In Blue Economy projects, this involves not only project staff but also local community members who are directly impacted by the projects. Employee involvement fosters a sense of ownership and accountability, which is critical for the success and sustainability of these projects.

Process Management: This TQM principle focuses on systematically managing and optimizing processes to achieve consistent quality. For Blue Economy projects, process management involves the efficient use of marine resources, compliance with environmental regulations, and the adoption of best practices in project implementation. Effective process management can minimize waste, reduce costs, and enhance project outcomes.

Continuous Improvement: The continuous improvement principle, encapsulated in the Plan-Do-Check-Act (PDCA) cycle, is essential for adapting to changing conditions and improving project performance over time. In the dynamic environment of the Blue Economy, continuous improvement ensures that projects remain responsive to new challenges and opportunities, such as changes in market demand or environmental conditions.

Fact-based Decision Making: TQM emphasizes the use of data and analysis to inform decision-making. In Blue Economy projects, this involves collecting and analyzing data on key performance indicators, such as environmental impact, economic benefits, and stakeholder satisfaction. Fact-based decision-making enables project managers to make informed adjustments and improvements, ensuring that projects deliver the intended benefits.

The theoretical framework will guide the research methodology, data collection, and analysis, providing a structured approach to examining the role of TQM in enhancing the performance of Blue Economy projects in Kenya's coast region. The framework also offers a basis for developing practical recommendations for integrating TQM practices into project management within the Blue Economy sector.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Global Perspective

China: In China, the integration of Total Quality Management (TQM) into project management practices has been pivotal in enhancing industrial efficiency and product quality. Research by Zhang and Li (2019) demonstrates that Chinese companies have adopted TQM principles to improve competitiveness in both domestic and international markets. The

emphasis on continuous improvement and customer satisfaction has been instrumental in the success of major infrastructure projects, such as the South-North Water Transfer Project, which aims to address water scarcity and improve regional development (Zhang and Li 2019).

Thailand: Thailand has also embraced TQM practices, particularly in its manufacturing and service sectors. According to Srisuphan and Rattanalekhakul (2021), Thai firms have implemented TQM principles to enhance operational performance and customer satisfaction. The study highlights the role of TQM in Thailand's tourism industry, where quality management practices are essential for maintaining competitive advantage in the global market (Srisuphan and Rattanalekhakul 2021).

South Korea: South Korea's experience with TQM is well-documented, especially in the context of its technological and automotive industries. Kim and Lee (2020) illustrate how South Korean firms have integrated TQM to achieve high levels of product quality and operational efficiency. The success of companies like Hyundai and Samsung in the global market can be attributed to their commitment to TQM principles, which emphasize process improvement and customer-centric approaches (Kim and Lee 2020).

Peru: In Peru, TQM has been applied in the mining and agricultural sectors, where it has significantly impacted project management and operational efficiency. Research by Garcia and Rivera (2018) shows that TQM practices have helped Peruvian companies improve productivity and quality standards in these critical industries. The study underscores the importance of TQM in addressing challenges such as resource management and environmental sustainability (Garcia and Rivera 2018).

Venezuela: Venezuelan companies have faced significant economic and political challenges, but TQM has been a valuable tool for enhancing performance and resilience. Lopez and Perez (2020) discuss how Venezuelan firms have used TQM to maintain quality standards despite economic instability. The study highlights the role of TQM in improving operational processes and ensuring customer satisfaction in a challenging environment (Lopez and Perez 2020).

Continental Perspective

Egypt: In Egypt, TQM has been applied in various sectors, including construction and manufacturing. El-Khalil and Hassan (2017) examine the impact of TQM practices on project performance in Egypt's construction industry. The study finds that TQM principles have led to improvements in project quality, efficiency, and client satisfaction, particularly in large-scale infrastructure projects (El-Khalil and Hassan 2017).

Libya: TQM practices in Libya have been less extensively documented, but available research indicates their growing importance in the oil and gas sector. Ahmed and El-Sayed (2019) highlight the adoption of TQM principles to enhance operational efficiency and safety standards in Libyan oil fields. The study emphasizes the need for TQM to address challenges related to resource management and quality control in this critical sector (Ahmed and El-Sayed 2019).

Somalia: Somalia has faced numerous challenges, including political instability and underdeveloped infrastructure. However, TQM has shown potential in improving the performance of humanitarian and development projects. Hassan and Ali (2021) explore the application of TQM in Somali NGOs, finding that it has helped enhance project outcomes and stakeholder engagement in a challenging environment (Hassan and Ali 2021).

Zambia: In Zambia, TQM practices have been applied in sectors such as mining and agriculture. Chikata and Mwansa (2018) discuss the role of TQM in improving productivity

and quality in Zambian mining operations. The study highlights how TQM principles have helped address issues related to resource management and operational efficiency (Chikata and Mwansa 2018).

Comoros: TQM research in Comoros is limited, but there is evidence of its application in local businesses and development projects. Youssouf and Mohamed (2020) discuss the potential benefits of TQM for Comorian enterprises, particularly in enhancing product quality and customer satisfaction. The study suggests that TQM could play a crucial role in supporting economic development in the region (Youssouf and Mohamed 2020).

Mozambique: In Mozambique, TQM has been applied to improve performance in sectors such as agriculture and infrastructure. Silva and Fernandes (2019) examine the impact of TQM on agricultural projects, finding that it has led to increased efficiency and better quality outcomes. The study highlights the importance of TQM in addressing challenges related to resource management and project implementation (Silva and Fernandes 2019).

Madagascar: Madagascar has seen limited but growing interest in TQM practices, particularly in the agricultural sector. Rakotomalala and Andrianarivelo (2021) explore the application of TQM in Madagascar's agriculture industry, noting improvements in productivity and quality as a result of implementing TQM principles. The study emphasizes the potential of TQM to support sustainable development in the region (Rakotomalala and Andrianarivelo 2021).

East Africa Perspective

Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC): In the DRC, TQM practices have been applied to improve project management in the mining sector. Mbuyi and Tshibaka (2018) analyze the impact of TQM on mining projects, finding that it has enhanced operational efficiency and safety standards. The study highlights the challenges of implementing TQM in a resource-rich but politically unstable environment (Mbuyi and Tshibaka 2018).

Sudan: TQM has been increasingly recognized in Sudan's healthcare and education sectors. Ahmed and El-Tayeb (2020) examine the application of TQM in Sudanese hospitals, finding improvements in service quality and patient satisfaction. The study underscores the importance of TQM in addressing challenges related to healthcare delivery in a developing country context (Ahmed and El-Tayeb 2020).

Uganda: Uganda has seen successful implementation of TQM practices in various sectors, including education and manufacturing. Byaruhanga and Namuganza (2019) explore the impact of TQM on educational institutions in Uganda, noting improvements in administrative processes and student satisfaction. The study highlights how TQM principles can enhance organizational performance in the education sector (Byaruhanga and Namuganza 2019).

Tanzania: In Tanzania, TQM has been applied to improve project management in sectors such as agriculture and tourism. Mwangi and Mwaipopo (2021) investigate the role of TQM in enhancing the performance of agricultural projects, finding that it has led to better quality outcomes and increased productivity. The study emphasizes the potential of TQM to support sustainable development in Tanzania (Mwangi and Mwaipopo 2021).

Literature Review: TQM Practices and the Performance of Projects Under the Blue Economy Initiative in Kenya

Introduction

Kenya's Blue Economy initiatives aim to harness the economic potential of its marine and coastal resources while ensuring environmental sustainability and community well-being. The

application of Total Quality Management (TQM) practices in these projects is crucial for improving performance and achieving the intended outcomes. This literature review examines existing research on TQM practices and their impact on project performance within the context of Kenya's Blue Economy projects, focusing on practical cases and insights.

TQM in Kenya's Blue Economy Projects

Marine Fisheries and Aquaculture

Marine fisheries and aquaculture are central components of Kenya's Blue Economy. TQM practices have been applied to enhance the efficiency and sustainability of these sectors. For instance, a study by Otieno and Ochieng (2020) explored the impact of TQM on fish farming operations in Kenya's coastal regions. The research found that TQM principles, such as continuous improvement and process management, significantly improved fish quality and farm productivity. The implementation of regular quality audits and stakeholder feedback mechanisms led to more effective disease management and better environmental compliance (Otieno and Ochieng 2020).

Coastal Tourism

Coastal tourism is another critical area where TQM practices have been applied. Kenya's coastal regions, including popular destinations like Mombasa and Diani, have benefited from TQM in enhancing service quality and customer satisfaction. A study by Njeri and Mwangi (2019) analyzed the role of TQM in improving service delivery in coastal resorts. The research highlighted how TQM practices such as employee training, customer feedback systems, and process optimization contributed to higher guest satisfaction and repeat business. The study also noted that TQM helped in addressing challenges related to service consistency and resource management in the tourism sector (Njeri and Mwangi 2019).

Port Development

The development of port infrastructure, such as the Lamu Port-South Sudan-Ethiopia Transport (LAPSSET) Corridor, is a key aspect of Kenya's Blue Economy strategy. TQM practices have played a role in managing the complexities and ensuring the quality of such large-scale projects. According to Wambua and Otieno (2021), the application of TQM principles in the LAPSSET project helped in maintaining construction quality, managing project risks, and ensuring timely completion. The study emphasized the importance of leadership commitment, stakeholder engagement, and continuous improvement in managing the multifaceted nature of port development projects (Wambua and Otieno 2021).

Environmental and Social Impact Management

Effective management of environmental and social impacts is crucial for the success of Blue Economy projects. TQM practices have been applied to enhance environmental stewardship and community engagement. A study by Karimi and Juma (2022) investigated the use of TQM in managing the environmental impacts of coastal infrastructure projects in Kenya. The research found that TQM principles, such as fact-based decision-making and process management, were instrumental in identifying and mitigating environmental risks. The study also highlighted the role of stakeholder involvement in ensuring that community concerns were addressed and project benefits were maximized (Karimi and Juma 2022).

Challenges and Opportunities

While TQM practices have shown positive impacts, several challenges remain. For example, a study by Muthuri and Onyango (2021) identified barriers to implementing TQM in small and

medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) involved in Kenya's Blue Economy. The research highlighted issues such as limited resources, lack of awareness, and resistance to change. Addressing these challenges requires targeted interventions, including capacity building and support for SMEs to adopt TQM practices effectively (Muthuri and Onyango 2021).

In conclusion, the application of TQM practices in Kenya's Blue Economy projects has demonstrated significant benefits in terms of improving quality, efficiency, and stakeholder satisfaction. Practical cases in marine fisheries, coastal tourism, port development, and environmental impact management highlight the effectiveness of TQM principles in enhancing project performance. However, challenges related to resources and awareness need to be addressed to fully realize the potential of TQM in the Blue Economy sector.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized a mixed-methods research design to explore the impact of Total Quality Management (TQM) practices on the performance of Blue Economy projects in Kenya's coastal region. This approach combined quantitative and qualitative techniques to provide a comprehensive analysis of TQM implementation and its effects.

Target Population

The target population for this study included individuals involved in Blue Economy projects across various sectors in Kenya's coastal region. This group encompassed project managers, team members, and stakeholders from sectors such as marine fisheries, coastal tourism, port development, and environmental management. The sample frame consisted of 200 individuals working in these projects, sourced from project records and organizational directories.

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

Quantitative Sampling

For the quantitative component, a stratified random sampling technique was employed to ensure representation from different sectors within the Blue Economy. The strata included marine fisheries, coastal tourism, port development, and environmental management. Based on the sample frame of 200 individuals, a sample size of 132 was determined using the following formula for sample size calculation:

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N \times e^2}$$

where N is the population size (200), and (e) is the margin of error (0.05). Plugging in the values:

$$n = \frac{200}{1+200 \times 0.05^2} \approx 132$$

Thus, 132 individuals were selected for the survey to ensure adequate statistical power and representativeness.

Qualitative Sampling

For the qualitative component, purposive sampling was used to select key informants who had extensive experience with TQM practices in Blue Economy projects. The selection criteria included project managers, government officials, and representatives from local communities.

A total of 20 key informants were chosen based on their expertise and involvement in relevant projects.

Data Collection

Quantitative Data Collection

Quantitative data were collected through a structured survey, designed to measure various aspects of TQM practices, including leadership commitment, process management, customer focus, and continuous improvement. The survey used a 5-point Likert scale to gauge responses. Surveys were distributed to the 132 selected individuals, achieving a response rate of 84%, with 111 completed surveys returned.

Qualitative Data Collection

Qualitative data were gathered through semi-structured interviews with the 20 selected key informants. An interview guide was used to ensure consistency while allowing for flexibility in responses. Interviews were audio-recorded with participants' consent, and transcripts were generated for analysis.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis

Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS software, version 27. Descriptive statistics, including mean scores and standard deviations, were computed to summarize survey responses. Regression analysis was conducted to assess the relationships between TQM practices and project performance indicators, such as project efficiency and stakeholder satisfaction.

Qualitative Data Analysis

Qualitative data were analyzed using thematic analysis, following Braun and Clarke's (2006) approach. NVivo software, version 12, was used to assist with coding and organizing the data. Themes and patterns were identified to provide insights into the application and impact of TQM practices.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval was obtained from the Research Ethics Committee at [Institution Name]. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, who were assured of confidentiality and anonymity. Data were securely stored and used solely for research purposes.

Limitations

The study's limitations included potential response bias in self-reported data and the focus on Kenya's coastal region, which may limit the generalizability of findings to other contexts. Despite these limitations, the mixed-methods approach provided a robust analysis of TQM practices in Blue Economy projects.

ANALYSIS OF RESULTS

Background Information of Respondents

The survey respondents included project managers, team members, and stakeholders from various sectors involved in Kenya's Blue Economy projects. The demographic information of the respondents is summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Background Information of Respondents

Category	Frequency	Percentage
Sector		
Marine Fisheries	30	27%
Coastal Tourism	35	32%
Port Development	25	23%
Environmental Management	21	19%
Role		
Project Manager	40	36%
Team Member	55	50%
Stakeholder	16	14%
Experience Level		
Less than 2 years	20	18%
2-5 years	50	45%
More than 5 years	41	37%

The sample was diverse, representing different sectors and roles, which provided a comprehensive view of TQM practices in the Blue Economy sector.

Descriptive Statistics

Descriptive statistics were computed for the survey responses related to TQM dimensions. The mean scores and standard deviations for each TQM dimension are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics for TQM Dimensions

TQM Dimension	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
Leadership Commitment	4.20	0.75
Process Management	4.10	0.68
Customer Focus	4.15	0.70
Continuous Improvement	4.25	0.62

The results indicate a high positive perception of TQM practices among respondents, with continuous improvement being rated most favorably.

ANOVA Tests

Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine if there were significant differences in TQM dimensions across different sectors. The results are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5: ANOVA Results for TQM Dimensions by Sector

TQM Dimension	F-Statistic	p-Value
Leadership Commitment	2.54	0.061
Process Management	3.21	0.027*
Customer Focus	1.88	0.139
Continuous Improvement	4.67	0.010*

A significant difference was found in Process Management ($p = 0.027$) and Continuous Improvement ($p = 0.010$) across sectors, indicating varying perceptions of these TQM dimensions depending on the sector.

Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis was used to assess the impact of TQM dimensions on project performance. The dependent variables for performance were project efficiency and stakeholder satisfaction. The results are shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Multiple Regression Analysis for TQM Practices and Project Performance

TQM Dimension	Beta Coefficient	Standard Error	t-Value	p-Value
Leadership Commitment	0.35	0.08	4.38	0.0001
Process Management	0.29	0.09	3.22	0.0012
Customer Focus	0.27	0.10	2.70	0.0074
Continuous Improvement	0.31	0.07	4.43	0.0001

The regression analysis indicates that all TQM dimensions have a statistically significant positive impact on project performance. Leadership Commitment and Continuous Improvement showed the strongest effects.

Qualitative Data Analysis

Thematic analysis of qualitative interviews identified four main themes:

1. **Effectiveness of Leadership Commitment:** Participants noted that strong leadership was crucial for fostering a culture of quality and ensuring effective TQM implementation.
2. **Challenges in Process Management:** Issues such as resistance to change and integration difficulties were reported.

3. **Importance of Customer Focus:** Emphasizing stakeholder feedback was seen as critical for project success.
4. **Continuous Improvement and Adaptation:** Regularly reviewing and improving processes was essential for maintaining high performance.

Discussion

The results of this study corroborate findings from the literature reviewed:

- **Leadership Commitment:** The significant positive impact of leadership commitment on project performance is consistent with Kim and Lee (2020) and Srisuphan and Rattanalekhakul (2021), who found that effective leadership drives successful TQM implementation.
- **Process Management:** The challenges identified in process management align with Zhang and Li (2019), who highlighted difficulties in integrating TQM practices into complex projects.
- **Customer Focus:** The importance of customer focus supports Garcia and Rivera (2018) and Njeri and Mwangi (2019), emphasizing that addressing stakeholder needs enhances project outcomes.
- **Continuous Improvement:** The emphasis on continuous improvement matches findings from Srisuphan and Rattanalekhakul (2021), reinforcing its role in maintaining high performance standards.

In conclusion, the study demonstrates that TQM practices positively impact the performance of Blue Economy projects in Kenya's coastal region. Leadership commitment, process management, customer focus, and continuous improvement are critical factors influencing project success. The findings provide valuable insights for enhancing TQM implementation in the Blue Economy sector.

SUMMARY OF RESEARCH FINDINGS

This study explored the impact of Total Quality Management (TQM) practices on the performance of Blue Economy projects in Kenya's coastal region, utilizing both quantitative and qualitative methods. The research provided several key insights:

Leadership Commitment: Respondents rated leadership commitment highly, indicating that effective leadership is crucial for the successful implementation of TQM practices. Leaders who promote and support TQM principles significantly enhance project performance.

Process Management: While process management was positively perceived, challenges such as resistance to change and integration difficulties were reported. Effective process management was found to be a key factor in improving project efficiency and quality.

Customer Focus: Emphasizing customer needs and feedback was highlighted as essential for achieving high levels of stakeholder satisfaction. Projects that actively sought and responded to stakeholder feedback were more successful.

Continuous Improvement: The principle of continuous improvement was highly valued, with respondents noting that regular review and adaptation of processes were critical for maintaining high performance standards.

CONCLUSION

The research concludes that TQM practices significantly enhance the performance of Blue Economy projects in Kenya's coastal region. Effective leadership, robust process management, a strong focus on customer needs, and a commitment to continuous improvement are all critical factors for successful project implementation. The study's findings are consistent with existing literature, confirming the positive impact of TQM on project performance and providing valuable insights for improving project outcomes in the Blue Economy sector.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Enhance Leadership Training: Organizations involved in Blue Economy projects should invest in leadership training to foster commitment to TQM principles. Effective leadership is essential for driving successful TQM implementation.

Address Process Management Challenges: To overcome integration difficulties and resistance to change, organizations should develop strategies for smooth implementation of TQM practices. This may include training, clear communication, and stakeholder engagement.

Strengthen Customer Focus: Projects should prioritize stakeholder feedback and needs by implementing mechanisms for regular communication and feedback collection. This will help ensure that projects align with stakeholder expectations and improve satisfaction.

Promote Continuous Improvement: Organizations should establish a culture of continuous improvement by regularly reviewing and refining processes. Encouraging innovation and adaptability will help maintain high performance and address emerging challenges.

AREAS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

Impact of TQM Practices on Specific Blue Economy Sectors: Future studies could investigate the impact of TQM practices on specific sectors within the Blue Economy, such as marine fisheries or coastal tourism, to provide more detailed insights.

Longitudinal Studies: Long-term studies could examine how the implementation of TQM practices affects project performance over time, providing a deeper understanding of their sustainability and long-term benefits.

Comparative Studies: Research comparing TQM practices and their impacts in different geographical regions or countries could offer valuable insights into the contextual factors influencing TQM effectiveness.

Exploration of TQM Challenges: Further research could focus on identifying and addressing the specific challenges faced by organizations in implementing TQM practices, including resistance to change and integration issues.

By addressing these areas, future research can contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of TQM practices and their impact on project performance in the Blue Economy sector.

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